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Title:

“Geometric Interpretation of Quantum Phase Evolution using De Moivre's Theorem”

Abstract:

This conceptual paper shows the Geometric Interpretation of Quantum Phase Evolution through ‘De Moivre's Theorem’. Previous paper on Quantum State Normalization and Z (Complex) Plane representations. Which shows how Repeated Phase Multiplication can be visualize as rotation in the Z (Complex) Plane. By using the Polar representation of Complex Number and the roots of unity. This paper provides an intuitive framework for understanding Phase Accumulation, Periodicity and State Evolution. The approach establishes a connection between Complex Analysis,

Engineering Mathematics and Geometric Reasoning showing an accessible Visualization of abstract Quantum concepts.

Introduction:

Complex Variables play an important role in Quantum Mechanics. Every Quantum State has Probability Amplitudes that's are generally Complex-Valued and may be expressed through Magnitude and Phase Components.

The Geometric Interpretation of Complex Number, that provides valuable insights into Oscillatory Phenomena, Wave Behaviour and Rotational Symmetry. Euler's Equation and De Moivre's Theorem establish a direct relationship between Complex Exponentials and Geometric Rotations.

The purpose of this paper is to explore how Phase Evolution may be interpreted Geometrically through repeated Rotations on the Complex Plane. Particular attention is given to the Roots of Unity and their connection to Discrete Phase States.

Mathematical Representation:

"Existence and Non-Existence as Quantum Probability: A Probability-Based Alternative to Schrödinger's Cat".

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15421043>

"Quantum Superposition as Unit Circle: A Geometric View of Normalization".

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17198290>

"Quantum State Normalization in Z (Complex) Plane: A Geometric Interpretation".

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19907566>

From Previous Papers:-

$$Z = r e^{i\theta}$$

$$\because Z = a + ib$$

By applying De-Moivre's Theorem:

$$Z^n = (r e^{i\theta})^n = r^n e^{in\theta}$$

$$= r^n (\cos n\theta + i \sin n\theta)$$

or equivalently,

$$(\cos\theta + i \sin\theta)^n = \cos(n\theta) + i \sin(n\theta)$$

Here, θ : Phase

$n\theta$: Phase Evolution

Repeated Multiplication: Quantum State

Rotation in Z (Complex) Plane

Suppose,

4th Roots of Unity (Unit Circle).

Here, $n=4$

$$z^4 = 1 \quad \text{i.e. } z_0, z_1, z_2, z_3$$

$$\text{as, } z^4 = 1 \Rightarrow z = 1.$$

Now,

$$z^4 = r^4 (\cos 4\theta + i \sin 4\theta) = 1$$

$$= 1 (\cos 0 + i \sin 0) = 1$$

$$\therefore z_0 = 1(\cos 0 + i \sin 0) = 1$$

$$z_1 = 1\left(\cos \frac{\pi}{2} + i \sin \frac{\pi}{2}\right) = i$$

$$z_2 = 1(\cos \pi + i \sin \pi) = -1$$

$$z_3 = 1\left(\cos \frac{3\pi}{2} + i \sin \frac{3\pi}{2}\right) = -i$$

Notation and Cross-Domain Interpretation:

This paper is on a **Cross-Domain Framework** combining concepts from Quantum Mechanics and Engineering disciplines such as Signal & Systems and Control Theory. The Imaginary unit is denoted by i in Physics and j in Engineering, both represent $\sqrt{-1}$.

In this paper, i is used in Quantum Mechanical expressions and while j is used when referring to Z-Plane (Engineering) representations. This distinction allows a unified interpretation of Quantum States and Engineering System representations within a common Complex-Plane Framework.

Quantum Phase Evolution:

A Complex Phase factor may be represented as:

$$e^{i\theta(n)}$$

As the phase changes, the Quantum State evolves according to

$$e^{i\theta} \rightarrow e^{i\theta(2)} \rightarrow e^{i\theta(3)} \rightarrow e^{i\theta(4)} \rightarrow \dots$$

These collections of Phase, plays a fundamental role in Quantum Physics and Quantum Technology.

Phase Evolution as Geometric Rotation:

Consider the Complex Variable in Polar Form.

$$Z = re^{i\theta}$$

By Applying De Moivre's Theorem:

$$\begin{aligned} Z^n &= (re^{i\theta})^n \\ &= (r^n) \cdot e^{i\theta n}. \end{aligned}$$

The Transformation is:

$$\theta \rightarrow n\theta$$

that indicates the repeated multiplication results in a multiplication of the Phase Angle (Rotation in Complex plane).

Geometrically, the corresponds to the rotation in the Z (Complex) Plane. For the point on the Unit Circle ($r=1$), the Magnitude remain Constant, while the Phase continuously Changing through Angular Displacement. Thus, Phase evolution may be visualized as a Rotational Motion on the Unit Circle, that's providing a Geometric Interpretation of Complex Quantum Amplitude.

Root of Unity($r=1$) and Rotational Symmetry:

The root of Unity gives one of the most elegant demonstration of Rotational Symmetry in the Z(Complex) Plane.

$Z^n=1$ (as Unit Circle).

The Equation is given by:

$$Z_k = e^{i(2\pi/n)k}, \quad k=0,1,2,\dots$$

These points lie on the Unit Circle and are equally spaced by an angle(θ).

$$2\pi/n=\theta(\text{Angle in Radian}).$$

n: Order of Symmetry.

Here, $n=4$ (i.e. Square); $2\pi/4 = \pi/2$ rad.

For the special case $n=4$

$$Z^4=1$$

The four Roots are:

$$1, i, -1, -i.$$

These roots divided the Unit Circle into four equal parts, each separated by an angle(θ) of $\pi/2$ rad.

The set of roots remains fixed, under successive Rotations of $2\pi/n= \theta$, showing Rotational Symmetry.

For $n=4$, the sequence:

$$1 \rightarrow i \rightarrow -1 \rightarrow -i \rightarrow 1$$

forms a complete rotational cycle around the Unit Circle.

∴ Summation of Roots Vectors on Unit Circle:

$$1+i+(-1) +(-i)$$

$$=0.$$

$$\sum Z_k=0.$$

From Geometrical Representation:

The Unit Circle represents all possible Phase Angles.

The Roots of Unity represents equally spaced Rotational Positions.

Equal Angular spacing shows Rotational Symmetry.

Potential Applications: A Cross-Domain Framework.

The Geometric Interpretation in the paper may provide useful insights in several areas where Complex Variable and Phase Relationship play a fundamental role to understand.

Quantum Mechanics:

Complex Phase factor are centre to Quantum State Evolution. The Geometric Visualization of Phase Evolution through De Moivre's Theorem, may help to understand the role of Phase in Quantum System.

Mathematical Physics:

The connection between Euler Equation, De Moivre's Theorem and Rotational Symmetry gives a Geometric Framework.

Complex Analysis:

The Root of Unity represent fundamental concept in Complex Analysis. Geometric Framework on the Unit Circle provides a clear idea of Rotational Symmetry and Periodic Function.

Signal & Systems:

Complex exponential is highly use in Fourier Analysis and Signal Representation. The Geometric Interpretation of Phase Rotation may help to visualize Sinusoidal Signal concepts.

Control Theory:

This method may help to understand Phase Stability Analysis of Dynamic Systems.

Engineering Mathematics:

This framework is an educational bridge between Complex Variable Mathematics and applications on Oscillation (Harmonic Function), Wave Function and Rotational Dynamic Systems.

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Conclusion:

The paper presented a Geometric Interpretation of **Quantum Phase Evolution** using **De Moivre's Theorem** and the **Z (Complex) Plane**. By relating repeated Phase Multiplication to Geometric Rotation and examining the **Roots of Unity**. The work provides an intuitive visualization of Phase Evolution and Rotational Symmetry. This conceptual framework establishes a connection between **Complex Analysis, Mathematical Physics, Engineering Mathematics, Control Theory, Signal & Systems and Quantum Mechanics** shows an accessible Geometric Perspective for understanding abstract Quantum concepts.

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